

Synthesis of Methyl Ester of Cascarrillic Acid

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The reactions of ethyl diethyl phosphonate acetate with heptanal yielded *Trans*-2 ethyl nonoate (I). LiAlH_4 reduction of (I) affords the corresponding allylic carbinol (II) which was converted to corresponding bromide (III) with phosphorus tribromide. The reaction of bromide (III) with cuprous cyanide in dimethyl sulphoxide followed by alcoholysis afforded the corresponding unsaturated ester (V). The compound (V) was subjected to Simmons Smith reaction to obtain the desired compound (VI).

THE essential oil derived from the bark of *Croton eluteria Bennett* contains cascarrillic acid. The structure of the compound has been established through spectral data of its methyl ester¹. It appears that no attempt has been reported to provide a synthetic evidence for the structure of Cascarrillic acid. The salient feature of the compound is the presence of cyclopropane ring at β - γ position to carboxylic group in the aliphatic acid. In this communication we wish to report a straightforward synthesis of the title compound. The key step in the synthetic scheme involves the formation of cyclopropane ring through carbene addition to the double bond of appropriate unsaturated ester. The carbene has been generated by reaction of Zn/Cu couple with methylene iodide².

By means of phosphonate variation of Wittig reaction heptanal was condensed with ethyl diethyl phosphonate acetate in the presence of NaH, using tetrahydrofuran as solvent. Ethyl diethyl phosphonate acetate was prepared from triethyl phosphite and α -bromo ethyl acetate by Michaelis Arbusov reaction. This resulted in the formation *trans*-2-ethyl nonoate^{3,4,5}. $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{film}}$ 1715, 1645, 975 cm^{-1}

(consistent with $-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}\text{C}-\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5$ grouping). The conjugated ester (I) was reduced with LiAlH_4 in benzene to bring about hydrogenation of ester grouping and to avoid hydrogenation of the conjugated double bond⁶. $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{film}}$ 3400, 1640, 970 cm^{-1} . The allylic carbinol (II) was converted into corresponding bromide (III) by reacting with phosphorous tribromide in ether in dark, which on further treatment with cuprous cyanide in dimethyl sulphoxide furnished *trans*-2-nonyl nitrile (IV). $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{film}}$ 2245, 990 cm^{-1}

(consistent with $-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}\text{C}-\text{CN}$ grouping). The

cyanide on alcoholysis with methanol and HCl gas⁷ yielded *trans*-3-methyl decanoate (V). $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{film}}$ 1730, 990 cm^{-1} .

I.

II. X = OH

III. X = Br

IV. X = CN

VI

Simmons Smith reagent was prepared from methylene iodide and Zn/Cu couple and β - γ -unsaturated ester (V) was subjected to carbene addition (twice) from this reagent. This furnished methyl ester of cascarrillic acid (VI). The purity of the compound (VI) was checked by TLC after distillation. The compound was characterized through IR and NMR spectra. $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{film}}$ 1740, 1250 (saturated ester), 3000, 1025 (cyclopropane), 850 cm^{-1} ; NMR (δ ppm) 0.25-1.0 (4H, m, cyclopropane), 0.85 (3H, s, methyl), 1.25

(10H, methylene), 2.18 (2H, d, $\text{CH}_2-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}\text{C}-\text{OCH}_3$), 3.6 (3H, s, OCH_3).

The spectral data of synthetic ester of Cascariilic acid (V) are comparable with the reported data given for the methyl ester of naturally occurring Cascariilic acid¹.

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